

STRUCTURAL-SEMANTIC TYPES OF CONCEPTS.

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ANNOTATION

This article describes the study of the term concept, its linguistic and cultural features and forms. The principles of the linguistic and cultural research of the concept and the methods of determining the linguistic and cultural characteristics of the concept are discussed, as well as the opinions expressed by famous linguists about them.

Key words: *Linguistics, concept, modern associations, cognitive concept, nominative density, paradigm of conceptualism, category apparatus.*

For a long time, researchers have been studying the ratio of components in one concept (or cultural phenomenon) and methods of their determination. It follows from the recognition of the concept with the content plan of the language sign that it includes all the communicatively important information except the reference. First of all, the indicators of the position of this sign in the lexical system of the language: if it includes paradigmatic, syntagmatic and derivational connections, the semantic content of the concept includes all pragmatic information related to the expressive and illocutionary functions of the linguistic sign. Another highly probable component of the semantics of the concept is the cognitive memory of the word: the semantic properties associated with the original purpose of the linguistic sign and the moral value system of native speakers. However, the most important thing here is the cultural and ethnic component that determines the specific features of the semantics of natural language units and reflects the "linguistic picture of the world" of the speakers.

Taking into account that the problems of studying the processes of conceptualization and categorization of a known reality are among the most urgent and urgent issues of cognitive linguistics, the description of the concept recognized by scientists as the main form of knowledge classification and the main means of conceptualizing reality, category, frame, gestalt, which has become a learning tool in cognitive linguistics and conducting wider scientific research on terms such as slot remains the most urgent task facing modern linguists in the world. At this point, it is appropriate to mention the foreign and local scientists who conducted research on the nature of the linguocognitive concept and its specific features: V. Von Humboldt, E. Sepir, B. Whorf, Dj. Lakoff, M. Minsky, R. I. Pavilenis, C. Fillmore, AA Potebnya, S. A. Askoldova, D. S. Likhacheva, N. D. Arutyunova, Yu. S. Stepanov, E. S. Kubryakova, A. P. Babushkin,

Z. D. Popova, I. A. Sternin, V. V. Kolesov, Sh. Safarov, D.U. Ashurova, A.E. Mamatov, M. Rasulova, G'.M. Hoshimov, J. Yakubov and others.

Categorization is a process of fundamental knowledge related to sorting and dividing into types all the various information that a person encounters every day. The distribution of objects into classes has a linguistic nature and can serve as material for studying the category process as a means of language knowledge and communication. Below, the concepts of categorization and frame in cognitive linguistics are covered in detail, definitions are given through the views of scientists, and the range of problems to be considered in a row is defined. First, what is a category and what are its aspects, secondly, what place do categories occupy in the cognitive cycle, thirdly, how to study categories by analyzing language units and which categories can be determined in the field of factor attribute knowledge.

That said, the interaction between languages and mental structures is a central problem in cognitive linguistics. Along with the modeling of speech and thought processes, the study of various knowledge, the study of important cognitive strategies, and the development of category theories further increase the relevance of this science.

Indeed, a significant part of life experience is conveyed to us through language; through language units of different levels, a person encodes the information processed by him, at the same time reflects his view of the world or the external world. In addition, categorization has a linguistic nature: the division of cognitive objects into types and classes is accompanied by a comparison of the value of assigning an object to a certain category based on the semantic content of its name, creating a connection of language.

For example, M.I. Rasulova's monograph is devoted to the lexical level of general linguistic categorization, and based on this issue, a number of problems of the language system, including the semantic field and the theory of lexical typology, are analyzed. In the monograph, for the first time, the issue of formation of linguistic typology as an independent discipline was considered. In this work, for the first time, a methodical analysis of the category of animacy in English and Uzbek languages was developed. Lexical categorization of linguistic units representing this category, mutual relations of phraseological and syntactic units, as well as lexicogrammatical differences of various words are revealed.

According to V. Maslova, the term "category" is widely used in philosophy, where it is considered one of the cognitive forms of human mental thinking. He

claims that in philosophy, categories are the most important things; is a general concept that reflects the phenomena of the objective world (classes such as time, time, space, motion, quality and quantity) and intersubjective communication.

It can be seen that the concept of category occupies one of the central places in modern linguistics, therefore the term category is explained below as a very relevant innovation in modern linguistic theory according to the semantic or cognitive approach: "In linguistics, a category is any element of a language family separated on the basis of any common feature. It is a set of some signs (parameters) that divides a set of the same language units into separate classes based on a certain quantity, which do not cross each other.

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